

Agronomic characteristics

Abscission layer in the rice pedicel

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The morphology of the abscission layer situated in the region between the pedicel and the rachilla of the spikelet

of Peta, IR8, IR22, and Sukhwel 20 was investigated at flowering and 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 days after flowering.

The abscission region of the pedicel in longitudinal view (Fig. 1) appears to consist of one to two layers of parenchymatous cells surrounded by layers of heavily lignified sclerenchymatous cells.

The abscission layer extends from the epidermis to the central vascular tissues in the pedicel. It does not cut right through the pedicel but leaves the

central vascular bundle and several layers of sclerenchyma tissue bordering the vascular tissues of the pedicel "intact."

The parenchymatous cells that make up the abscission layer constitute a line of weakness in the pedicel, with the central vascular bundle (0.1 mm in diam) and the sclerenchymatous tissue situated between (or bordering) the vascular bundle and the abscission layer, forming the resistance tissues of the pedicel (Fig. 2).

Comparative studies on pedicel morphology near the abscission layer of four rice varieties indicate that the shedding ability of rice spikelets might be controlled by 1) the number and size of

1. The region of the abscission layer in the pedicel of rice (longitudinal view): A = abscission layer, G = sterile glume, S = sclerenchymatous cell layers, V = vascular tissues.

2. Light micrographs of longitudinal sections of the abscission layer in Sukhwel 20 (top) and Peta (bottom). Note the difference in thickness of the sclerenchymatous cell layers (S) bordering the abscission layer (A) and the vascular tissues (V) x 420.

Morphological features of the abscission layer in the pedicels of 4 rice varieties, Hongkong.

Variety	Cells in the abscission layer (no. in section)	Size of parenchymatous cells in the abscission layer (mm x 10 ⁻³)	Sclerenchymatous cells (no. of layers) ^a	Thickness of the sclerenchymatous tissue ^b (mm x 10 ⁻³)	Width of the central vascular bundle (mm)
Peta	21-22	5-7	5-6	70-100	0.1
IR8	20-21	5-7	5-6	70-90	0.1
IR22	19-20	5-7	5-6	70-90	0.1
Sukhwel 20	15-18	7-10	4-5	30-50	0.1

^aNumber of sclerenchymatous cell layers bordering the abscission layer and the central vascular tissues of the pedicel.

^bSclerenchymatous tissue bordering the abscission layer and the central vascular bundle of the pedicel.

parenchymatous cells present in the abscission layer, and 2) the number of sclerenchymatous cell layers bordering the abscission layer and the central vascular tissues of the pedicel. These two morphological features vary somewhat between the rice varieties (see table). Among the four varieties, Sukhwel 20 is the only one with fewer cells in both regions. Moreover, the parenchymatous cells in the abscission layer of Sukhwel 20 appear slightly larger than

those in Peta, IR8, and IR32, but the sclerenchymatous cell tissue bordering the central vascular bundle and the abscission layer is much narrower.

Since Sukhwel 20 tends to shed its spikelets with relative ease, it may be

reasonable to conclude that varieties with relatively larger parenchymatous cells in the abscission layer and a thinner sclerenchymatous tissue (fewer cell layers) bordering the abscission layer and

the central vascular bundle of the pedicel are essentially more fragile (i.e. mechanically weaker). Consequently their spikelets are more susceptible to shattering. ■

Performance of some long-duration semidwarf rice cultures in relation to their suitability for medium lowland cultivation during the wet season

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An investigation to identify promising cultures for medium lowland cultivation (20 to 40 cm water level) used materials selected from coordinated trials at Chinsurah, Cuttack, and IRRI, Philippines.

Twelve long-duration entries suitable for medium lowland cultivation were tested in 1976 and 1977 (see table).

Yield of long-duration semidwarf rice cultures on medium lowlands during 1976-77 wet season, India.

Culture	Yield (t/ha)	
	1976	1977
Pankaj (check)	5.7	4.5
IET2911	4.6	3.2
IET3257	4.6	2.9
IR32	4.5	3.4
HTA448	4.5	2.8
IET4087	4.4	3.1
IET3235	4.2	3.3
HTA108	3.8	3.5
IR34	3.8	3.0
Pankaj (M) 91	3.1	4.2
CNBP153-58-2	3.5	3.0
CNBP-134-134-1	3.4	2.3
LSD (.05)	0.4	0.6

The experimental design was randomized complete block with four replications. Plots were 4.8 x 2.6 m with plant spacing of 20 x 15 cm and fertilizer applications of 80 kg N/ha, 40 kg P/ha, and 40 kg K/ha.

Pankaj was statistically superior to all the other varieties in 1976. Yields from IET2911, IET3257, IR32, HTA448, IET4087, and IET3235 were statistically the same. Pankaj, though the highest yielder in 1977, was statistically equal to Pankaj (M) 91. Yields from all the other cultures were statistically the same. The yield deviation between the 2 years may have been caused by environment. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Gall midge- and bacterial blight-resistant varieties for Madhya Pradesh, India

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Gall midge and bacterial blight are the two most frequent biological stresses on the paddy crop of eastern Madhya Pradesh. The average farmer cannot

afford plant protection measures against the two stresses. A breeding program for resistance to them was initiated at Raipur. Four improved varieties of different maturity groups, resistant to gall midge and bacterial blight and resistant to moderately resistant to several other pests, were developed. The varieties have performed well in farmers' fields and abundant seed is now available. Details of the varieties are:

Variety	Cross	Yield (t/ha)	Grain quality ^a	Days to maturity	Pest reaction ^b
R2384	R68-1/Jaya	3.4	MS	125	GM(R), SB(MR), LF(MR), BPH (MR), BLB(R)
R35-2752	IR22/W1263	3.7	LS	128	GM(R), SB(R), GLH(MR), BPH (MR), LF(MR), BB(R)
R35-2750	IR22/W1263	4.6	LB	132	GM(R), BB(R), HEL(R), RTV (R)
R35-2751	IR22/W1263	4.2	LB	135	CMCR), BB(R)
RP9-4	(check)	3.3	LB	135	GM(R)
RPW6-17	(check)	4.3	LB	140	GM(R)

^aMS = medium slender, LS = long slender, LB = long bold. ^bGM = gall midge, SB = shoot borer, LF = leaf folder, BPH = brown planthopper, GLH = green leafhopper, BB = bacterial blight, HEL = Helminthosporium brown spot, RTV = rice tungro virus, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

Sources of resistance to rice ragged stunt disease

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Rice ragged stunt, a virus disease transmitted by the brown planthopper, was first observed in the Philippines in 1978 and has since been reported in Thailand, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and in West Bengal, Orissa, and Tamil Nadu states in India. AICRIP screening programs were initiated to find sources of resistance to the disease. During 1979 kharif, 80 varieties were screened in the greenhouse. Most of the high-yielding semidwarfs were susceptible (50-80% infection). But despite artificial inoculation, certain varieties – Pokkali, Getu, PTB18, PTB33, T141, Hitam, Benong 1, Tamiang, Slammat, Benong 3, Boak, and Boegimba – produced no symptoms. ■